

IODINE DEFICIENCY IN WOMEN OF CHILDBEARING AGE

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Annatment: this article describes the anatomical physical as well as physiological development of the organism of women of childbearing age, the effects of iodine deficiency treatments on later pregnancy as well.

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Usually women of childbearing age say that many people have an understanding of women around the age of 20-35. But in girls, in the period from adolescence to adulthood, the appearance of menstrual Silk, the development of the endocrine system, the accelerated work of the harmonies, and physical changes in teenage girls begin. In particular, we can cite the development of the mammary glands as an example. And it is in this state that the activity of the uterus in our girls also begins to develop. And in girls, cases of preparation for childbirth begin. So if we check the statistics we will not go wrong if we say that women whose childbearing age is between 13 and 45 years old.

This means that in women of childbearing age, although iodine deficiency is not noticeable, it actually also has very bad consequences. The original causes of iodine deficiency are disorders of the functioning of the thyroid gland, as a result of which iodine deficiency is caused by insufficient iodine supply to the body. The thyroid gland is one of the largest glands and is located in the neck area. Anatomically obtainable bolsak will be up to 30-50mm in length. Kalingili is equal to 10-20mm. It can be shaped like a horseshoe shawl. As for the internal structure of the gland, it consists of vesicles in the population. They are called phalicles. Inside the phalanges there is a protein substance rich in iodine, called tereiglobulin, which is a liquid colloidal substance. The gland is somewhat larger in females than in males. It is not only considered a marphalagic state, but also has an important physiological significance. Because women are 3-4 times more common in women than men.

The gland is located somewhat above children. The gland produced by the thyroid gland is called thyroxine. It is this harmony that is important for the organism. Thyroxine has an effect on growth on the body. The effect on metabolism is also great. When the thyroid gland does not develop well, the body stops growing. Even if the activity of the gland increases, the body is

damaged by terioxin. As a result, teritoxycosis occurs. Thyroid-producing Harmons also control the breakdown of protein fat carbohydrates.

From this, other factors also influence. In some parts of our country, insufficient iodine content in drinking water leads to an enlargement of the gland.

Sometimes it is also possible to increase the function of the gland, as the norm is the violation of the meiori, while the gland does not enlarge. Literally every activity of the thyroid gland is an important stage for the body.

It is controlled to prevent iodine deficiency even during pregnancy , to ensure that both the fetal woman and the unborn child have sufficient iodine intake. Treatment measures are carried out if a disease is detected, leading them to constant control. Prevention of iodine deficiency is one of the most important priority goals. It means that it is recommended to periodically go to a doctor's appointment, consult a doctor, go to a specialist endocrinologist if the disease is to be detected, although there are no complaints. If iodine deficiency is detected, it is recommended to take drugs through the drug expert.

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